

Genotype × system of planting interaction for flowering. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Direction of change in transplanting compared with direct seeding ^a (d)	Genotypes
0 (no change)	<i>Group 1</i> B2997-CTB-60-3-3, Rath, Sakun, Kn 361-1-B-6 IR6828-2-4, B635-2, NDR95, NDR311, Narendra 1
+ 1	<i>Group 2</i> NDR102, Jhona 349, Dular
+ 2	Dhaneshwar, Lalnakanda
+ 3	NDR80, DJ29, Tulzapur-1, Tetep
+ 4	Karahani, IAC25, D3-29
+ 5	Kinandang Patong, NDR118, Halamaldia, Ranikajal-A, Brown Cora
+ 6	Mala J15, Sarya-A, Lalmati
+ 7	Kalkeri, Dudhi A, Lalmati
+ 8	Kachni, N22, NDR88, NDR119
+ 9	Black Bagari, Kudia, Mutmuriya, NDR97
+10	Bagari White
+11	Culture 62
+12	Jalsar, Kolhapur Scented, NDR85
+13	NDR308
+14	IRAT115
+15	Dehula A, NDR115
+16	Bagari, Sawani, Ketki
+17	NDR132
-1	<i>Group 3</i> Mutmuri A, Mircirak, IR15784-14, IR4895-1-2-1-8
-2	Annapurna, IRAT107
-3	ASD7, ARC10372, IET7041, NDR83
-4	Kiran, IET6973, IET7564
-5	CR245-1, NDR87
-6	Kanchan, Govind
-7	MW10, IET6639

^a+ = increase (delay), - decrease (earliness).

maturity is an important economic trait, and differences of even a few days can influence productivity, adaptability, cropping intensity, and cropping sequence. Compared with direct seeding, transplanting appears to extend the time to 50% flowering or by about 1 wk. However, observation of flowering among certain varieties under the two planting systems revealed differential behavior for that trait. One hundred genotypes with both dwarf and tall backgrounds from national and exotic sources were therefore grown simultaneously under the two systems.

Three groups were apparent (see table). The first group showed stable flowering behavior under both planting systems, the second exhibited a 1- to 17-d delay in flowering with transplanting, and the third showed 1-7 d earliness with transplanting.

The differential flowering responses of rice genotypes to direct seeding and transplanting might stem from their genetic variability with respect to plasticity for nutritional and hormonal imbalances within the plants. Seedlings uprooted for transplanting are subjected to physical mutilation that suddenly arrests the supply of water, nutrients, and other metabolites. There is also a time lag between uprooting of seedlings,

their transplanting, and further establishment in the soil. During this period the seedlings are subjected first to drought stress, then to flooding in the puddled field.

These sequential conditions are known to reduce cytokinin and gibberellin synthesis in the roots and also their transport to shoots. The mutilation effects may vary in magnitude in different genotypes, depending upon the growth behavior of the root system in the nursery and the delicateness of the seedlings.

Reduction in days to flowering in several rice genotypes on transplanting is still a baffling situation. □

Variability in bud number, bud length, and ratoon tillering in four rice varieties

S. Gupta, S. Das, B. Patra, and S. K. Bardhan Roy, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, West Bengal, India

We studied ratoon tillering ability in three photoperiod-sensitive varieties — NC365, FR13A, and Patnai 23 — and a longduration, high yielding variety — IET5656 — sown on 15 Nov 1985 in Chinsurah.

The main crop was harvested May 1986. N fertilizer (10 kg/ ha) and irrigation water were applied to plots of all varieties 4 d after harvest. Viable buds per main tiller, bud length on the main tiller, and ratoon tillers per plant were measured for three cutting heights (see table).

Cutting height caused a significant difference in number of viable buds on the main tiller; however, the interaction effect of variety and cutting height was not significant. Viable buds were less with the ground level cut than with higher level cuts. The correlation between viable buds per main tiller and ratoon tillers per plant over all cutting heights was statistically nonsignificant but showed a moderately positive relationship in FR13A, Patnai 23, and IET5656.

Bud number, bud length, and ratoon tillering in 4 rice varieties at 3 cutting heights. Chinsurah, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Cutting height (cm)	Viable buds (no./ main tiller)	Bud length on main tiller (mm)	Ratoon tillers (no./plant)
<i>NC365</i>			
5	1.9	5.2	8.5
15	2.3	5.7	7.4
30	3.2	4.9	6.6
<i>FR13A</i>			
5	1.9	5.5	8.9
15	2.9	6.3	8.5
30	3.3	5.7	10.4
<i>Patnai 23</i>			
5	2.7	16.1	9.7
15	3.1	31.9	9.5
30	4.1	68.0	10.5
<i>IET5656</i>			
5	2.4	4.7	2.3
15	3.5	5.7	1.7
30	4.2	8.2	7.1
<i>F-value^a</i>			
Variety	25.05**	5.63*	3.27
Cutting height	54.11**	4.7*	5.7**
Variety × cutting height	0.96	3.87*	4.14*
CD (0.05)			
Variety	0.3	23.9	-
Variety × cutting height	0.3	10.1	0.4

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels.

The average bud length on the main tiller for different cutting heights did not differ among the varieties except in

Patnai 23, where bud length was generally longer and showed a distinct lengthening trend with increased cutting. This is attributed largely to a varietal difference and to a variety \times cutting

height interaction in respect to bud length.

Varietal differences in ratoon tillers per plant were not significant, but the effect of cutting height and the

interaction effect were. A higher cut produced a higher number of ratoon tillers. Bud length was not influenced by viable bud number. \square

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Demonstration of rice parboiling using an improved wood stove

H. M. Wilson, Association Pour la Productivité (APP)/Togo, c/o USAID, Via Air Pouch (Lome I.D.), Washington, D.C. 20520, USA

The initial demonstration of parboiling of rice among growers of the Zio River Irrigated Perimeter in Togo, held by APP in 1985, did not result in adoption of the practice even though several advantages were clear: a 6% increase in milling yield, cleaner and fewer broken grains, and less insect damage during storage. Nonadoption was attributed to poor selection of participants and lack of follow-up.

The APP agronomist felt that there were enough potential benefits to warrant reintroduction of the technique. A brief technical bulletin explaining the process and its benefits was distributed to extension agents. The targets selected this time were APP clients who were life-long residents of the village of Assome. The program included a fuel-saving wood stove and fuel wood production using *Leucaena leucocephala*.

Three separate demonstrations covered 1) the building of mud stoves, 2) parboiling, and 3) cooking and taste tests. The first showed the need to produce fuel wood as well as save fuel. Planting *Leucaena* adjacent to the drying floor and warehouse was suggested.

Parboiling was done in a modified metal drum. The parboiled rice gave a milling yield of 69% versus 62% for the nonparboiled.

In the third demonstration, held on a

market day, women were invited to taste parboiled and nonparboiled rice with a sauce. They expressed preference for parboiled rice.

Influence of planting date on milling performance of rice varieties under delayed harvesting

F. Cuevas-Pérez and L.E. Berrio, IRTP Latin America, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), Apartado Aereo No. 6713, Cali, Colombia

The evaluation of advanced lines for milling quality by comparing samples harvested at 20-25% moisture content with those left standing in the field 10-15 additional days is normal practice in the rice breeding program at CIAT. Such an approach is expected to predict milling performance at the farm level accurately.

We studied the milling performance of varieties CICA8 and Oryzica 1 for seven planting dates in Palmira, Colombia, during Feb 1985-Aug 1986. Plantings were simultaneous on all but the third planting date, when CICA8 was planted 1 wk earlier to obtain simultaneous maturity. Two samples of 1 kg of rough rice each were taken twice for each variety and planting time — when grain moisture was 20-25%, and 12-15 d later. Milling evaluations were done using standard McCill laboratory equipment.

The effect of delayed harvest on the head rice yields varied according to planting date (see figure). CICA8 showed no reduction in three of the seven evaluations, and Oryzica 1 in four.

A typical farmer who plants 1 ha to rice and grows 2 crops/yr could realize \$300-400 more profit by adopting parboiling. \square

Head rice yield of 2 rice varieties harvested at 20-25% moisture content and delayed for 12-15 d, for 7 planting dates. Cali, Colombia, 1985-86.

Screening rice genotypes for tolerance for delayed harvest in the field would thus require consideration of environmental effects. \square

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